

LEXICAL CONSTRUCTION OF CHARACTER NAMES IN "ANTHOLOGY OF MUSSIDI'S SHORT STORIES" BY BRUNEI DARUSSALAM WRITER, MUSSIDI

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Abstract

This research aims to analyze the use of lexical construction of character names in Mussidi's short story collection. This research also reviews the use of character names related to Malay culture set in Brunei Darussalam. This research uses a qualitative descriptive approach and corpus linguistics. Data collection was carried out using corpus data documentation techniques. The results of this research reveal several lexical variations in character names in general, namely animals, gender terms, proper names, names of prophets, common nouns, creator/creator, formal profession/position title, non-formal profession/position title, pronominal, and transcendental figure. Lexical variations in character names related to Malay culture. This research also found several kinship terms related to Malay culture.

Keywords: Lexical Construction, Kortara, Korpus Nusantara.

1. INTRODUCTION

Lexical construction is a very interesting thing to discuss. This is based on lexical studies that associate meaning with the words used [1]. The relationship between a meaning and the words used in this discussion is not tied to the context which generally depends on the speech situation. The meaning in question is the meaning of the general use of the word.

Theoretically, lexical is a study that discusses the meaning of words in the language used. Lacková [2] and Schmid [3] defines lexical theory as a study that links the meaning of language to the words used. This relationship can also be illustrated by reference to the language used. This definition provides an explanation of lexical studies which is attractive to linguists, because it links meaning to words used in a particular language. Ravshanovna [4] also mentions lexical relationships with certain cultural conditions. One clear proof of the relationship between lexical and certain cultures is the use of the word *Isteri* in Malay in relation to the status of a woman who is married to a man.

The interest of academics in the field of linguistics in lexical studies can be found in several previous studies, including Baryshnikova [5], Demidova [6], Zeng [7], Siallagan [8], and Goziyah [9]. Baryshnikova [5] researched the lexical comparison between French and Russian. Demidova [6] researched lexical and grammatical matters in Chinese. Zeng [7] researched lexical issues in English. Siallagan [8] researched the use of Indonesian lexical language in the movie. Goziyah [9] researched the use of lexical and grammatical aspects in Indonesian song lyrics. Based on the description of previous research, it can be understood that research in the lexical field has its own attraction. Apart from that, the description also explains that specific research on lexical background in the country of Brunei Darussalam has not been carried out.

Therefore, the author examines the lexical construction of character names in a work originating from Brunei Darussalam

The topic selection for the lexical construction of character names in a work originating from Brunei Darussalam focuses on a literary work. This work is an anthology of Mussidi's short stories. This research is expected to be able to review the lexical terms contained in the characters of these literary works, and analyze the meanings of their use. The terms reviewed in this research are not only limited to the lexical construction of character names in general, but also terms for character names related to Brunei Darussalam culture.

2. METHOD

The research approach used in this research is descriptive qualitative, which takes the form of specific descriptions and explanations [10], [11], [12], and [13]. The advanced method approach for this research is the corpus linguistic method, which utilizes the digital corpus linguistic application KORTARA (Korpus Nusantara) [14], [15], and [16].

This research uses documentation data collection techniques, which are sourced from corpus files in the Korpus Nusantara application. The analysis technique used is computational linguistic techniques, which utilize computer system applications to manage research data digitally.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Systematically, there are several findings regarding the lexical construction of character names in Mussidi's short story collection. These findings can be formulated in a construction based on type, namely (1) animals, (2) gender terms, (3) kinship terms in Malay, (4) proper names, (5) names of prophets, (6) common nouns, (7) creator/creator, (8) formal profession/position title, (9) non-formal profession/position title, (10) pronominal, and (11) transcendental figure. To clarify, here is the table.

Table 1: Data Finding

No	Types of Character Names	Number of Character Names	Total Frequency
1	Animal	3	82
2	Gender terms	5	449
3	Malay Kinship Terms	21	715
4	Proper name	86	1313
5	Prophet's name	1	52
6	Common nouns	3	159
7	Creator/creator	2	87
8	Formal profession/title	13	207
9	Non-formal profession/position title	5	41
10	Pronouns	9	6774
11	Transcendental figure	2	45
		150	9924

Apart from the table above, lexical construction data findings can also be seen based on bar charts. As shown in this bar charts.

Figure 1: Bar Charts Data Finding

Based on the diagram that has been presented, it can be understood that lexical use indicating proper names occupies the most dominant position. Apart from the type, the number presented can also be seen from the total frequency.

3.1 Animal Character Names

The lexical construction of character names contained in the "Mussidi Short Story Anthology" by Brunei Darussalam writer Mussidi, in the first type, namely animals, consists of three character names, namely the lexical name of the character *Si Belang*, *Buaya*, and the lexical name of the character *Anjing*.

3.2 Gender Terms Names

The lexical construction of character names contained in "Mussidi's Anthology of Short Stories" by Brunei Darussalam writer Mussidi in the second type, namely gender terms, consists of five character names, namely lexical names of *pemuda-pemuda*, *pemuda*, *wanita*, *perempuan*, and lexical names of *lelaki* characters.

3.3 Malay Kinship Terms

The lexical construction of character names contained in the "Anthology of Mussidi's Short Stories" by Brunei Darussalam writer Mussidi in the third type, namely kinship terms in Indonesian, consists of twenty-one character names, namely the lexical names of the characters, *emak-emak*, *ibunya*, *Cucu Tuan Rumah*, *menantunya*, *Bapa*, *Isteri Samin*, *Emak*, *ibu*, *isteriku*, *Suami*, *bini-bini*, *bapanya*, *cucu*, *adikku*, *bapaku*, *Anaknya*, *Suaminya*, *Abang*, *isterinya*, *anak-anak* and lexical name of the *isteri*.

3.4 Proper Names

The lexical construction of character names contained in the "Anthology of Mussidi's Short Stories" by Brunei Darussalam writer Mussidi in the fourth type, namely personal names, consists of eighty-six character names, namely the lexical names of characters *Awang Muntil*, *Hajah Sainah*, *Siti Soleha*, *Syarif Ali*, *Dang Sumur*, *Hajah Latifah*, *Hajah*

Sufiah, Saloma, Si Dunggu, Si Tanggang, Siti Fatma, Siti Hawa, Siti Rahmah, Tuan Syahminan, Aimullah, Damit, Hasiah, Hj.Marsal, Hj.Matassan, Syamsul, Matnor, Si Damit, Si Tolol, Syahminan, Syarif Ahmad, Tajulmuluk, Talib, Tuan Punya Kedai, Hajah Russimah, Haji Sabtu, Sabriah, Setan, Syafik, Awang Karmun, Si Mawarti, Encik Badawi, Pak Ali, Si Manis, Dang Ambun, Haji Syamsuddin, Si Suriah, Tuk Tamir, Haji Ahim, Mohd Ali, Gayah, Haji Talib, Syamsiah, Sarkawi, Si Anu, Awang Saiful, Gergasi, Normah, Bibah, Judin, Tuan Peter Baldwin, Laila, Marianne, Nurlaila, Pak Sabtu, Semaun, Tuan Syaiful, Siti Rahayu, Tuan Syekh, Haji Zainal, Damong, Syahrir, Abdul Hamid, Abu Daud, Mamat, Safwan, Samin, Dang Sara, Tuan Haji, Haslan, Muntil, Dabat, Pak Cik, Dollah, Said, Pak Budin, Budin, Si Matnor, Syafinah, Betty, Tuk Amir, and the lexical name of the character Pak Seman.

3.5 Prophet's Name

The lexical construction of character names contained in "Mussidi's Short Story Anthology" by Brunei Darussalam writer Mussidi in the fifth type, namely the name of the prophet, consists of one character's name, namely the lexical name of the character *Adam*.

3.6 Common Nouns

The lexical construction of character names contained in "Mussidi's Short Story Anthology" by Brunei Darussalam writer Mussidi is in the sixth type, namely general nouns, consisting of three character names, namely lexical names of *orang*, *mayat*, and lexical names of *orang-orang*.

3.7 Creator

The lexical construction of character names contained in the "Mussidi Short Story Anthology" by Brunei Darussalam writer Mussidi in the seventh type, namely the creator/creator, consists of two character names, namely the lexical name of the character *Tuhan* and the name of the character *Allah*.

3.8 Format Profession/title

The lexical construction of the names of characters contained in the "Anthology of Mussidi's Short Stories" by the writer of Brunei Darussalam, Mussidi in the eighth type, namely profession/formal title, consists of thirteen names of characters, namely the lexical names of figures such as *pegawai-pegawai*, *Pejabatnya*, *Jururawat*, *Ketua Pejabat*, *Gurubesar*, *Ustaz Sadikin*, *Penghulu*, *Polis*, *Tuan Penghulu*, *datuk*, *Doktor*, *Tuan Imam* and lexical names of *Guru*.

3.9 Non-formal Profession

The lexical construction of character names contained in the "Anthology of Mussidi's Short Stories" by the writer of Brunei Darussalam, Mussidi in the ninth type, namely profession/non-formal position title, consists of five character names, namely lexical names of characters *Tukang Kebun*, *Tukang Pukul*, *Pelayan*, *Tuan Rumah* and lexical name of the *majikan*.

3.10 Pronouns

The lexical construction of character names contained in the "Anthology of Mussidi's Short Stories" by the writer of Brunei Darussalam, Mussidi in the tenth type, namely pronouns, consists of nine character names, namely the lexical names of *kita*, *kamu*, *Dia*, *kami*, *kau*, *mereka*, *saya*, *aku* and lexical character's *ia*.

3.11 Transcendental Figure

The lexical construction of character names contained in the "Mussidi Short Story Anthology" by Brunei Darussalam writer Mussidi in the eleventh type, namely transcendental characters, consists of two character names, namely the lexical name of the *Syaitan* character and the lexical name of the *Malaikat*.

Based on the explanation of the data found regarding the lexical construction of character names, it can be understood that the lexical construction used generally refers to the use of words in general. However, there are several things that make this finding unique, namely the use of kinship terms in Malay, professional terms in Malay, and personal names which are also related to Malay culture.

The finding of the term kinship in Malay is in the form of the names of *emak-emak, ibunya, Cucu Tuan Rumah, menantunya, Bapa, Isteri Samin, Emak, ibu, isteriku, Suami, bini-bini, bapanya, cucu, adikku, bapaku, Anaknya, Suaminya, Abang, isterinya, anak-anak, isteri*. The names of the figures above are related to Malay kinship terms because the position of each figure's name has different functions in culture. W. Rusbiyantoro [17] said that the term kinship in Malay can be a greeting that has a close relationship.

The finding of names of figures related to professions or titles in Malay culture can also be seen in the use of the word *Penghulu, Tuan Penghulu, and datuk*. N. Sari [18] also mentioned that the term title or profession in Malay culture can also be found in the titles given to someone.

Findings of personal names of figures related to Malay culture can also be seen in the use of words of *Awang Muntil, Hajah Sainah, Siti Soleha, Syarif Ali, Dang Sumur, Hajah Latifah, Hajah Sufiah, Saloma, Si Dunggu, Si Tanggang, Siti Fatma, Siti Hawa, Siti Rahmah, Tuan Syahminan, Aimullah, Damit, Hasiah, Hj.Marsal, Hj.Matassan, Syamsul, Matnor, Si Damit, Si Tolol, Syahminan, Syarif Ahmad, Tajulmuluk, Talib, Tuan Punya Kedai, Hajah Russimah, Haji Sabtu, Sabriah, Setan, Syafik, Awang Karmun, Si Mawarti, Encik Badawi, Pak Ali, Si Manis, Dang Ambun, Haji Syamsuddin, Si Suriah, Tuk Tamir, Haji Ahim, Mohd Ali, Gayah, Haji Talib, Syamsiah, Sarkawi, Si Anu, Awang Saiful, Gergasi, Normah, Bibah, Judin, Tuan Peter Baldwin, Laila, Marianne, Nurlaila, Pak Sabtu, Semaun, Tuan Syaiful, Siti Rahayu, Tuan Syekh, Haji Zainal, Damong, Syahrir, Abdul Hamid, Abu Daud, Mamat, Safwan, Samin, Dang Sara, Tuan Haji, Haslan, Muntil, Dabat, Pak Cik, Dollah, Said, Pak Budin, Budin, Si Matnor, Syafinah, Betty, Tuk Amir, and Pak Seman*. This was also stated by W. Rusbiyantoro [19] who discovered the term proper name in Malay culture in his research. The term proper name in Malay culture is not included in the term kinship. However, it is still classified as a noble title in Malay culture.

Theoretically, lexical construction of character names is a way of forming character names. This means that a character's name can be formed in various ways, such as giving a name according to regional language or culture, giving a name according to the characteristics or nature of the character, or giving a name according to a certain incident or event. Alip [20], Faizatun [21], and Rahmawati [22] also suggested that lexical constructions associated with names or figures will produce a meaning associated with certain words.

This lexical construction is also related to a particular characteristic, trait, or culture, which describes a character. Lexical links with character names refer to the

relationship between the meaning of the words used in the character's name and the meaning of the words used in general language. An example of a lexical connection with a character's name is the use of the name *Datuk* in Malay which refers to an honorific or nickname for a man. Apart from that, in the Minang language, the word *Datuk* can also refer to a grandfather. These examples are evidence of the link between the lexical construction of character names and certain cultures.

4. CONCLUSION

The findings of this research reveal that the lexical construction of character names in Mussidi's short story collection is very diverse. The lexical construction of the character's name is also related to cultural elements in Brunei Darussalam, such as the use of Malay kinship terms, personal names, God, formal professions, non-formal professions, and transcendental beings. This research also reveals that the lexical terms used in a language can be associated with a particular culture. In this research, the lexical construction of character names reveals a small part of Malay culture in Brunei Darussalam.

Authors' Contributions

Ermanto has contributed to developing ideas and writing scientific articles. Vicno Triwira Dhika JR has contributed to writing scientific articles and data management. Havid Ardi has contributed to article writing and translation. Novia Juita has contributed to the development of the concept of writing scientific papers.

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